

PRESERVING VIDEO DVDs

A Long Journey Towards Preservation and Access

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Abstract - Video DVD is a very popular media to disseminate videos, offering a variety of challenges that needs to be addressed in order to be properly preserved. This paper examines the efforts of the National Library of France to ingest, preserve and give access to its entire DVD collection. It shows that among the multiple choices the best ones are often oriented by the community.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Presented to the public in 1995, the DVD (Digital Versatile Disk) system was invented to allow the dissemination of videos in digital form, making a huge improvement over the older analog VHS tape. It combines a standard for storing multiple video titles, combining streams of video, audio and subtitles, as well as a state-machine allowing the programming of the navigation and interaction of the user by means of a simple remote device. As a format, it is therefore halfway through a video and a multimedia one.

From a preservation point of view, many challenges arise:

1) The media itself, even if it can last some decades, needs to be dematerialized to ensure the durability of the content.

2) The format is not public: the specifications managed by the "DVD Forum" can be purchased after having signed a non-disclosure agreement that forbids any communication.

3) Various anti-piracy protections make the copy very hazardous: the CSS (Content Scrambling System) protects the content while a region code restricts the use of a DVD in specific defined geographic zones.

Yet, being a hugely successful media to commercialize and distribute movies, more than a hundred thousand of those entered the video collection of the library by legal deposit, making it an important media to take care of and to be able to give access to.

This article presents the gradual understanding and improvements of the National Library of France (BnF) towards the preservation of DVDs.

II. FROM HACKERS TO LIBRARIANS

Since the 1990s up to this day, video DVDs that are commercialized in France are deposited to the BnF as required by the law on legal deposit. Toward the end of 2000s, a number of medium types, including DVDs, were deemed at risk, their end of life being unsure. At the time, it was already understood that the first step in trying to preserve the content of a DVD was to rip it, that is to say: extracting its content onto hard drives.

An important difficulty to overcome, then, was the anti-piracy protections (aka cyphering) of DVDs used by the industry. Fortunately, as soon as 1999, hackers made public the first DeCSS program [1], used to disable it. This made possible to elaborate programs to copy their content. In France, the law for the "copie privée" (first invented in Germany and becoming standard at least in Europe) allows every individual that purchases a media to make a copy of

it to ensure continuous access of the original media (article L122-5 of the Intellectual Property Code). This makes the accessibility of such programs possible. Using the legal exception on intellectual property for libraries, the BnF was able to conduct the backup of its collection. Over time this resulted in the copy of approximately 135 000 discs.

This cannot be understated: while the law gave the library both the mission and the right to do so, it is the work of enthusiastic hackers that first gave librarians the means to preserve DVDs (as well as CDs and other mediums), even though these tools were often disparaged as piracy software.

III. ACCESSING A BUNCH OF FILES

Once unscrambled, a DVD is an ISO/UDF filesystem [2] containing a structure of files that respects a given template. Namely, two subdirectories (VIDEO_TS and AUDIO_TS) must exist as well as a number of files with a fixed naming, leading to the well-known structure illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Structure of a DVD

At that time, we didn't know much more about the DVD format, apart from the fact that VOB files carried the videos themselves. Therefore, we treated the content of the filesystem as an opaque format and simply copied everything in our systems [3].

In order to have a complete lifecycle [4], we needed a way to give access to this content. Fortunately, the work already done by DVD enthusiasts made it possible. We would deploy VLC [5] media player (open source software) on specially prepared workstations, as it is able to play DVD files on disk.

In the same way the work of retro-engineering done by a small community of hackers allowed to back up our DVDs, another work of retro-engineering [6][7] done by enthusiast allowed to play those backups. Without this work, it would have been vain to back up the DVDs in the first place.

IV. NEW AMBITIONS FOR THE 2020s

In 2019 the library started a program aiming among many other things:

- to streamline access of audiovisual material across the whole library, using web technologies and no specialized equipment.
- to merge the audiovisual repository into the "Scalable Preservation and Archiving Repository" (SPAR) [8], including every DVD.

Regarding DVDs, these two aspects were treated in the same period of time in part by the same set of people, which allowed to inform both the preservation aspects of the migration and its diffusion ones.

A. Extracting Each Video Individually

One of the library's ambition for the 2020s was to provide an easy access to the DVD collection through a web browser across the entire library. Since a DVD has a volume of up to 9 GiB, we needed to find a way to stream effectively its content.

The first option was to transform the content of a DVD into a series of videos, including of course the audio and subtitle streams. Since we wanted to stream the whole content, every video had to be extracted: the main one as well as bonuses. The transformation of the video stream itself is quite easy and well documented, producing a set of MP4 files.

For the audio, the same language can be present multiple times either because of technical alternatives (stereo versus 5.1) or because of different kind (normal, audio description for visually impaired or even director comments). So, the "best" track for each language needs to be chosen.

For subtitles, not only do we have the same issues, but a more technical obstacle exists. The subtitle tracks in a DVD are made of images intended to be overlaid on the original video. Since MP4-TT (used for subtitles in an MP4) is a text format, the images need to be extracted, transformed into text via OCR processing and tagged with the correct timestamp to synchronize the text with the underlying video.

Figure 2. DVD as a collection of videos

While this is doable (we managed to convert and give access to 5 000 DVDs this way, see Figure 2), it leads to hazardous results and the interactive part of the DVD as well as its descriptive information (being artworks in the menus) are lost. We managed to give access to the principal video content but we lost the very nature of the DVD in the process.

B. Repackaging the DVD Content as Filesystem

In the mean time we were conducting a migration of the audiovisual repository into SPAR, our main preservation system. As we worked on the DVD collection, we took a closer look at the files constituting it. As it is well known in the preservation community, preserving the bits is not enough if you don't know what they represent. More theoretically: we need to capture the Preservation Description Information (PDI) [9].

Very briefly, the IFO files (and the backup files, BUP) store the metadata needed to find the information about the video, sound and subtitle tracks on the disk while the VOB files carry the content itself (as interlaced MPEG streams). In terms of identification, the IFO and BUP formats were identified by PRONOM since 2012, by `file` since 2020 and by `tika` since 2024. So, we knew how to identify these files (finding an adequate MIME type), but not how to characterize them (extracting metadata). The naïve way of doing this migration would have been to keep this structure of files “as is” and simply identify (and not characterize) each one of them. But then, how would we make sense of this structure as a whole? Such a bunch of files, with its opaque structure hiding the titles and their relations (main title, bonus, etc.) didn't seem practical. Last but not least, we found that the IFO files mentioned exact locations of chunks on the media. In order to make the information in the IFO files accurate, the files needed to be located in the original sectors of the media.

A better way to preserve these DVDs would then be to repackage those files in an ISO/UDF filesystem that reproduces the original media by the help of tools like `mkisofs` [10]. A DVD is then a single file, which is itself a filesystem containing a normalized set of files, recognizable by DVD players like VLC. Preservation-wise, this is way more satisfactory and we are still able to show them to the public on specialized equipment as we did previously. More on that later.

But how to characterize such an object? We would like to capture for each DVD what its content is and what alternatives are provided. Even though programs like `1sdvd` may provide some information, we weren't satisfied by their lack of formalism which doesn't allow to manipulate and index it. Moreover, in our system, the audio and video content are usually described using the MPEG-7 schema [11]. Now that we have a single file, we would like to characterize it as we do for MP4 files for instance.

As said before, DVDs are not single video, nor single streams. So, we need to extract the information for each video title as well as each track. Fortunately, MPEG-7 has the notion of *Collection* of titles. Yet it is limited and we still needed to extend its schema to allow a title to have multiple tracks with their specificities (language, visually or hearing impaired, technical alternatives, ...). We designed an extended schema that allows this.

Sponsoring the MediaArea team, the `mediainfo` tool [12] was improved to be able to process an entire DVD and retrieve all the needed information in an extended-MPEG-7 formalism [13]. Since we now repackaged them as ISO/UDF, MediaArea extended `mediainfo` to be able to browse the files in an ISO9660 filesystem as if they were present unpackaged on disk.

C. Streaming the Repackaged DVDs

With all this work on repackaging DVDs as ISO/UDF filesystems, it was time to review its diffusion across the library.

With the apparition of the Web Assembly (WASM) technology [14], it is now possible to compile and execute pure C programs in a browser context. So, we sponsored the VideoLabs team that is responsible for VLC media player, that we already used in its desktop version to display DVDs. They were able to create a specific build of VLC called `VLC.js` by recompiling the program in WASM and

providing the needed interface in JavaScript so that a DVD can be displayed and interacted with (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. DVD player in a browser

A last issue was to make it streamable, as the whole ISO image of the DVD couldn't be allocated in the browser's memory, nor did we want any delay before starting to play it. Fortunately, we remembered that DVDs are designed to be read sector by sector (of 2KiB each) on modest equipment. That is to say: they are actually designed to be streamed, albeit not over a network. Since modern networks have huge bandwidths and low latencies, they may well be able to support this kind of streaming. Presenting ISO files using the "Range request" protocol [15] allowed to mimic the behavior of a living-room DVD player, addressing specific data chunks as needed. Once this extension was implemented both on our file servers and in VLC, we were able to give access to entire DVDs using a virtual remote control on a browser.

By using the latest evolutions of the browser environment, we are now in the position to end the cycle and provide our readers in all our reading-rooms with access to a DVD with the same user experience (including introductory advices, menu navigation and access to bonus features) as they might expect.

V. CONCLUSION

We can see here a trend where, in order to preserve such formats, the preservationist community need to wait long enough for it to have lost its commercial attraction (because it's replaced by new alternatives) as well as waiting for the "fan" community [16] to provide the tools to make the needed operations feasible and trustworthy.

It has to be noted that the "DVD Forum" has ceased its activities since January 1st of 2025 and is supposed to have deposited the specifications at the National Diet Library (NDL) in Japan. So, the question

of accessing this documentation should be resolved by the mere passing of time.

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Thomas is the coordinator of digital production at BnF, where he has worked as a software engineer for over 30 years. He has always been interested in digital objects, ranging from access on public workstations to his involvement in BnF's repository (SPAR). He regularly collaborates on various open source software.

Jordan joined the National Library of France in 2016, where he worked since then as a functional analyst engineer for its preservation system (SPAR).

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